

Radiation Retinopathy in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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PURPOSE

To review the clinical course and spectrum of ocular injury in patients treated with radiation for malignant tumors of the head and neck.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

The charts of all patients seen at the King Khaled Eye Specialist Hospital in the last 15 years with external beam radiation injury to the retina were reviewed retrospectively.

RESULTS

Fourteen (9 men and 5 women) relatively young (mean age 35.9 years) patients were identified with radiation injury to the retina (14), cornea (2), lens (3), and optic nerve (6) secondary to radiation therapy (mean 6000 cGy) for nasopharyngeal carcinoma (ten patients) and other brain, perinasal, and facial tumors (four patients).

CONCLUSION

Typical visual loss was not severe. The most profound visual loss occurred with radiation injury to the optic nerves and chiasm rather than retina alone. Visual function was usually maintained during the follow-up period with appropriate therapeutic intervention.

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RADIATION RETINOPATHY¹⁻⁷ IS A POTENTIAL complication of high dose external beam radiation given in the setting of certain intracranial, orbital, and facial tumors.^{3,8-13} It requires careful ophthalmologic follow-up and treatment in order to maximize residual vision.¹⁴⁻¹⁷

We have reviewed the experience of the King Khaled Eye Specialist Hospital (KKESH) since its opening in December 1982. The focus of this project is to sensitize the ophthalmologic, radiation therapy, and general medical communities in Saudi Arabia to radiation retinopathy so that the occurrence and visual consequences of this potentially devastating complication can be minimized.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Using hospital and physician records, we identified as many patients as possible who were seen at KKESH between December 1982 and September 1998 with radiation retinopathy due to external beam radiation therapy and who had one or more complete ophthalmologic examinations documented in the hospital chart. Radiation retinopathy was defined as a retinal microangiopathy occurring in a patient with a history of external beam radiation therapy to the head or neck.⁵ Patients with radiation retinopathy occurring as the result of radioactive plaque treatment for retinoblastoma or melanoma were excluded.

RESULTS

The fourteen patients (9 men and 5 women) with radiation retinopathy identified for this review are listed in Table 1 in order of increasing visual loss in at least one eye at last examination. This group represented the full spectrum of

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Table 1. Demographic information.

Patient	Age / Sex*	Tumor	cGy	Fraction/ Duration	Chemotherapy	Months to Symptoms
1	30 M	Glioblastoma			No	
2	56 M	NPC			No	
3	34 M	NPC / PD	6000	30/90 days	No	11
4	37 F	Antrum / ethmoid sinus	6820	31/68 days	Yes	44
5	35 M	NPC	6660	37/56 days	No	36
6	31 M	NPC	7000	35/90 days	Yes	12
7	47 F	NPC	6000	30/60 days	Yes	36
8	39 M	Right parotid			No	3
9	32 M	NPC / UD	6600	39/59 days	Yes	45
10	29 F	NPC	6500		No	72
11	52 M	NPC	6500	25/30 days	Yes	48
12	22 F	Right trigeminal recess	4000	20/30 days	Yes	60
13	15 M	NPC		two course	Yes	12
14	43 F	NPC	6600	33/49 days	Yes	48

* Age (years) at the time of initial radiation therapy

cGy = centigray; NPC = nasopharyngeal carcinoma; PD = poorly differentiated; UD = undifferentiated

radiation injury to the afferent visual apparatus with patients exhibiting radiation injury to the lens (patients 4, 5, 9), the globe (patient 13), and optic nerves (patients 3, 5, 10, 11, 12, 14) as well as the retina. Radiation retinopathy varied from mild (Fig. 1) to pre-proliferative (Fig. 2) and proliferative (Fig. 3) retinopathy. The patient with most severe visual loss (patient 14) had mild radiation retinopathy with radiation injury to the intracranial optic nerves and chiasm (Fig. 4).¹⁸⁻²¹

Information regarding tumor histology and radiation dosages and regimens were commonly not available in patient charts. Patients were contacted directly in order to acquire additional treatment records or information, but unfortunately, quantitative treatment information was sometimes not available. Ages ranged from 15 to 56 years (mean 35.9 years). Patients had received 4000-7000 cGy (mean 6000 cGy) of external beam radiation for nasopharyngeal cancer (ten patients), glioblastoma, squamous cell carcinoma of the perinasal sinuses, epidermoid cancer of right trigeminal recess, and parotid carcinoma (1 patient each). They were seen at KKESH 3-72 months after radiation (mean 36 months). This information is summarized in Table 2.

The presenting symptoms and initial clinical findings, treatment, and clinical course of the 14 cases of radiation retinopathy are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. Some patients had already received ophthalmologic care elsewhere before coming to KKESH. The ten patients with nasopharyngeal cancer had more severe visual loss on

average than the four patients irradiated for other reasons, possibly because the afferent visual system was more completely contained within the radiation ports used for nasopharyngeal cancer. Visual loss was most profound in patients with injury to the retrobulbar optic nerves and chiasm (patient 14) or to the globe (patient 13), and in patients with radiation papillopathy (patients 10 and 11). When retinal abnormalities were the predominant cause of symptoms, visual loss due to macular ischemia was typically worse than visual loss due to macular edema.

Visual loss from retinal involvement was variable and often did not result in progressive visual loss during the follow-up period despite the presence of proliferative changes. Patients whose visual loss was most severe were also the patients whose visual loss progressed the most during the follow-up. The only exception to this rule was patient 14, who had progressed to blindness in both eyes while followed at another institution. Patients whose vision improved the most during follow-up included those who underwent cataract extraction for radiation lenticular changes (eg. patient 4, whose right eye improved from counting fingers to 20/40) or who underwent a vitrectomy for vitreous hemorrhage (e.g. patient 8 whose left eye improved from counting fingers at 1' to 20/300).

In this small group of fourteen patients, there were no statistically significant correlations between visual outcome, radiation dosage, latency to symptoms, sex, or age. The patient group includes individuals irradiated for a

Table 2. Radiation retinopathy: presenting symptoms and clinical findings.

Patient	Presenting Symptoms	OD Initial examination	OS Initial examination
1	decreased VA OD	VA 20/25; NVE with mild vitreous and subhyaloid hemorrhage, IRMA, telangiectatic capillaries, microaneurysms	VA 20/20; mild vascular abnormalities
2	decreased VA OS	VA 20/20; normal examination	VA 20/25; hard exudates, telangiectatic capillaries, microaneurysms
3	decreased VA OU : OD>OS	VA 20/40; s/p PRP, mild disc pallor; cotton wool spots, macular capillary dropout	VA 20/100; s/p PRP, mild disc pallor; cotton wool spots, macular edema
4	decreased VA OU	VA CF 5; moderate cataract	VA 20/160; mild cataract, NVE, microaneurysms, IRMA, and preretinal hemorrhage
5	decreased VA OU : OD>OS	VA 20/160; pale disc, telangiectatic capillaries in posterior pole with irregular enlargement of foveal	VA 20/50; pale disc, telangiectatic capillaries in posterior pole with irregular enlargement of foveal
6	decreased VA OU	VA 20/125; macular microaneurysms and capillary dropout; intraretinal, preretinal, and vitreous hemorrhage	VA 20/100; NVE; macular microaneurysms, capillary dropout, and hemorrhage
7	decreased VA OU : OS>OD	VA 20/125; NVD, cotton wool spots, macular edema, vitreous and subhyaloid hemorrhage	VA 20/300; s/p PRP, severe macular capillary dropout and edema
8	decreased VA OS	VA 20/80; cataract, hard yellow exudates and hemorrhages	VA CF 1; cataract, hard yellow exudates and hemorrhages, preretinal hemorrhage
9	decreased VA OD	VA 20/400; NVE, preretinal hemorrhages and macular edema	VA 20/30; small areas of capillary dropout and microaneurysms
10	decreased VA OU	VA 20/50; NVD, disrupted foveal avascular zone, IRMA	VA 20/40; NVE, mild disc swelling
11	decreased VA OU : OS>OD	VA 20/160; papillopathy	VA 20/200; papillopathy
12	decreased VA OU	VA HM; NVE, macular ischemia, optic pallor	VA CF 3; NVE, macular ischemia, optic pallor, and vitreous hemorrhage
13	decreased VA OU : OD>OS	VA HM; sterile corneal ulceration	VA 20/125; mild disc pallor, macular hemorrhages and edema
14	sudden blindness OS, then OD	VA NLP; optic atrophy	VA NLP; optic atrophy

VA= visual acuity; CF= counting fingers; HM= hand motions; LP= light perception; NLP= no light perception; PRP= panretinal photocoagulation; IRMA= intraretinal microvascular abnormalities; NVD= neovascularization disc; NVE= neovascularization elsewhere.

Table 3. Radiation retinopathy: treatment and clinical course.

Patient	Follow-up (months)	OD Treatment	OD Evolution	OS Treatment	OS Evolution
1	3	PRP	VA 20/40; regression of NVE	none	VA 20/25; no change
2	60	None	VA 20/20; no change	none	VA 20/40; more microaneurysms and capillary dropout; macular edema
3	11	PRP, focal rx	VA 20/50; no change	PRP; focal rx	VA 20/80; no change
4	2	ECCE/IOL	VA 20/40; macular RPE changes	PRP	VA 20/100; dense cataract
5	50	ECCE/IOL	VA 20/100; increased disc pallor and size of foveal avascular zone	ECCE/IOL	VA 20/80; increased disc pallor and size of foveal avascular zone
6	12	PRP; vitrectomy	VA 20/80; perimacular vascular leakage	PRP	VA 20/200; progressive disc pallor and vascular changes
7	3	PRP; grid rx	VA 20/160; mild macular edema	PRP; grid rx	VA 20/200; involution of NVE
8	48	PRP; ECCE/IOL	VA 20/160; NVE regression cryotherapy; vitrectomy	PRP; ECCE/IOL	VA 20/300; macular ischemia
9	15	PRP; grid rx	VA 20/400; NVE regression	None	VA 20/30; capillary dropout and microaneurysms
10	15	PRP	VA 20/80; NVE; progression of vascular abnormalities	PRP; focal rx	VA 20/400; macular edema, IRMA, disc edema
11	18	hyperbaric oxygen	VA CF 5; development of opticociliary shunt vessels, progressive optic atrophy	hyperbaric oxygen	VA CF 5; development of opticociliary shunt vessels, progressive optic atrophy
12	12	PRP	VA LP; vitreous hemorrhage	PRP	VA 20/400; pale disc, attenuated blood vessels, ischemic maculopathy
13	48	conjunctival flap	VA NLP; phthisis bulbi	Diamox	VA 20/125; no change
14	14	none	VA NLP	None	VA NLP

VA= visual acuity; CF= counting fingers; HM= hand motions; LP= light perception; NLP= no light perception; PRP= panretinal photocoagulation; IRMA= intraretinal microvascular abnormalities; NVD= neovascularization disc; NVE= neovascularization elsewhere. RPE= retinal pigment epithelium; ECCE= extracapsular cataract extraction; IOL= intraocular lens

Figure 1. (A) Fundus photograph of left eye of patient 5 showing optic atrophy and mild changes of radiation retinopathy including inferonasal atrophy of the retinal pigment epithelium and telangiectatic capillaries. (B) Fluorescein angiography of the same eye showing telangiectatic capillaries and irregular enlargement of the foveal avascular zone.

Figure 2. (A) Fundus photograph of the left eye of patient 2 with moderate changes of radiation retinopathy including microaneurysms, exudates, and macular edema. (B) Fluorescein angiography of the same eye.

variety of tumors who experienced visual loss because of radiation injury to the globe and anterior visual system in addition to radiation retinopathy. If the analysis is limited to the six patients receiving radiation for nasopharyngeal cancer who experienced visual loss predominantly because of radiation retinopathy (patients 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9), a correlation is apparent between worse visual acuity and longer latent period from radiation to onset of symptoms ($r=-0.88$; $p=0.0203$). A strong association (falling short of statistical significance) is apparent between worse visual acuity and younger age ($r=0.75$; $p=0.0514$). No statistical association was apparent between visual outcome and radiation dosage in this restricted group. The possible contributory effect of medical problems such as diabetes²² or adjunctive therapy such as chemotherapy cannot be assessed in this small group of patients who were treated for different reasons using different protocols (using different chemotherapeutic regimens) at different institutions. For example, both diabetic patients received chemotherapy.

DISCUSSION

The patient group reported here is relatively small and probably highly selected according to criteria that can be only partially defined. Each patient was irradiated in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia for a tumor involving the nasopharynx, intracranial space, or perinasal sinuses. The patients seen at KKESH survived long enough after radiation to develop radiation retinopathy, the onset of which typically occurs one or more years after radiation is completed. No data is available regarding the total number of patients irradiated in the Kingdom for tumors near the visual apparatus or the total number of such patients surviving a period of time appropriate to potentially experience radiation retinopathy. Many patients developing visual loss after radiation therapy are undoubtedly cared for at the institution that organized the radiation treatment. KKESH is the largest eye facility in the region, but the criteria for referral of patients with radiation

Figure 3. (A) Fundus photograph of the right eye of patient 7 with severe changes of radiation retinopathy including capillary dropout, telangiectatic vessels, neovascularization of the disk, and pre-retinal hemorrhage. (B) Fluorescein angiography of the same eye confirming the presence of microaneurysms and avascular areas, and enlargement of the foveal avascular zone.

Figure 4. (A) Sagittal T1 weighted spin echo sequence showing swollen appearance of the chiasm in patient 14. (B) Same sequence with gadolinium injection shows the pathological enhancement of the chiasm related to radiation induced vascular changes. (C) Axial fast fat suppressed T1 weighted sequence (also known as fast field echo or gradient echo sequence) with gadolinium demonstrates enlargement and abnormal enhancement of the chiasm and intracranial portion of the left optic nerve in the same patient.

retinopathy to this center from other medical centers and regions of the Kingdom are not clearly delineated.

Radiation therapy was the primary treatment modality for each patient in this series. The high incidence of nasopharyngeal cancer in this group reflects the very high incidence of nasopharyngeal cancer in the Kingdom.²³ Young people are particularly at risk, resulting in the surprisingly young average age of our patients. Tumors treated with radiation therapy in Saudi Arabia are frequently large and associated with metastases, and radiation therapists need to strike a difficult balance between increasing the chance of survival with larger radiation doses and decreasing the chance of visual loss with smaller radiation doses. It is truly tragic to survive a potentially lethal malignancy at a young age only to experience profound visual loss due to radiation injury to the visual apparatus. On the other hand, survival itself may well depend on a larger radiation dosage.

Every patient reported here received 4000 cGy or more with the average dosage being approximately 6000 cGy to the region of the visual apparatus because of tumor location. Previous reports regarding radiation retinopathy^{7,12,13,16,17} and radiation injury to the afferent visual system²⁰ have documented that the radiation exposure experienced by our patient group is well within the range that causes radiation injury to the visual apparatus (although occasionally smaller doses can cause injury as well).^{24,25} Therefore, the occurrence of radiation injury in each patient was an expected potential complication. Interestingly, the most profound visual loss in this group was not due to radiation retinopathy but to radiation injury to the globe (patient 13, right eye) and the retrobulbar afferent system (patient 14, both eyes).

It is difficult to compare this series of patients to previous reports of patients with radiation retinopathy^{7,9-13,16,17,26} because the combination of tumors treated here is unusual due to the large representation of nasopharyngeal cancer, because of poorly defined referral patterns, and because of variable treatment regimens tailored to the clinical setting. All of the patients with proliferative retinopathy received panretinal photocoagulation,¹⁷ as well as some patients with pre-proliferative macular edema.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ One of our patients with bilateral radiation papillopathy was treated with hyperbaric oxygen, but unfortunately, vision did not improve. This treatment has been suggested for radiation injury to the retrobulbar optic nerves and chiasm^{27,28} and remains controversial.²⁰

The average final visual acuity in this series was 20/80, and it is important for ophthalmologists to realize that visual loss in radiation retinopathy is often not profound.^{13,16,17} Patients in this small series who had the longest latent period prior to ophthalmologic evaluation had the worst visual outcomes, implying that continued and careful ophthalmologic follow-up after radiation may well be important to visual outcome. Appropriately timed focal and panretinal photocoagulation, vitrectomy, and cataract extraction seemed able to halt progression of visual loss in most patients during the follow-up periods represented here even though fluorescein angiography frequently documented continued progression of microvascular disease.^{5,6,26} It seems likely, therefore, that patients with substantial radiation exposure to the visual apparatus would likely benefit from regular, planned care provided at a major ophthalmologic center.

Ophthalmologists, radiation therapists, and general physicians should learn to recognize radiation retinopathy so that patients can receive timely treatment. Patients with radiation retinopathy will most commonly complain of progressive, painless visual blurring in one or both eyes over a period of months. Usually the ophthalmologic and funduscopic examination contains the explanation of a patient's visual loss with visible microvascular changes that are similar to diabetic retinopathy.⁵ On occasion, retinal changes may be relatively subtle and not apparent to non-ophthalmologists or even to ophthalmologists without the benefit of fluorescein angiography.^{5,6,25} Gradual progression of visual loss is commonly due to progressive macular or lenticular changes. More rapid and profound loss of vision occurs in the setting of radiation papillopathy or radiation injury to the retrobulbar afferent system. Radiation papillopathy usually is known to have bad visual prognosis, although the visual acuity of at least one eye with radiation papillopathy (patient 11, right eye) remained 20/80 at the time of the last examination more than 7 years after radiation. A relatively normal funduscopic examination in the face of severe recent visual loss probably implies injury to the retrobulbar optic nerves and chiasm.²⁰ Magnetic resonance imaging is usually diagnostic in this setting^{18,29-31} and is also the diagnostic tool of choice to evaluate the patient for possible compressive injury to the afferent system due to tumor recurrence.

Certain issues related to the care of this patient group are scientific to Saudi Arabia. In general, patients did not bring medical records with them to KKESH, and they were typically unable to give accurate and detailed histories of their medical problems and treatments. Patients

were frequently unaware of tumor histology and basic information regarding treatment protocols. They did not know the names of treating physicians, although all of the present patient group were able to provide the names of their treating institutions. Unfortunately, it proved very difficult to collect information regarding diagnosis and treatment protocols from outside institutions. Conversely, it was also not clear from the review of these patients' KKESH charts that KKESH physicians had provided continuing feedback to treating institutions. Patients with radiation retinopathy who have been treated at one institution and then receive care for their ophthalmologic problems at another institution are one of many examples where better communication between major medical centers in the Kingdom could dramatically benefit patient care.

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